

Memorandum of Understanding

between

Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH
52425 Jülich
Germany

– hereinafter referred to as Forschungszentrum Jülich –

and

Frontiers Media SA
Avenue du Tribunal Fédéral 34
1005 Lausanne
Switzerland

– hereinafter referred to as Frontiers –

- both together referred to as Parties -

concerning a National Open Access Publishing Framework for Germany

Preamble

Frontiers and Forschungszentrum Jülich have a common goal of making science open.

The Parties aim to establish a pilot project that will enable researchers at the Helmholtz Centres to publish in Frontiers' journals at no (direct) cost to the researchers. It will also simplify and centralize the submission and invoicing process through university libraries. The project is initially intended to cover the Helmholtz Centres – the members of the Helmholtz Association – but will also provide an opportunity for all German research institutions and universities to participate in this arrangement. Once established, this can be used as a way of together exploring ever-better open access and funding models for the future.

The Parties mutually see this as an important step towards finalizing a National Open Access Framework for Germany with the objective of making scientific research immediately free to access. This goal is in line with the strategic objectives of the large-scale open access transformation as defined by Germany's Alliance of Science Organizations and the international funders' initiative cOAlition S (coalition-s.org), which requires that from 2021, scientific publications that result from research funded by public grants must be published in compliant open access journals.

Frontiers and Forschungszentrum Jülich discussed on several occasions the basic possibilities and principles for the Pilot National Open Access Publishing Framework for Germany (hereinafter referred to as "Framework"). The Parties have developed in these discussions a basic understanding of the mutual demands and main principles for which the Parties are aiming. They now intend to enter into specific negotiations on the contract (hereinafter referred to as "Agreement"), to be concluded which will encapsulate the Framework as summarised below.

I. Subject matter of the negotiations

The main principles for which the Parties are aiming can be summarised as follows:

1. General principles:

- The Framework will be open to all member institutions of Projekt DEAL (projekt-deal.de) which includes more than 700 publicly and privately funded academic and research organizations in Germany.

- The Framework will ensure that identical terms and benefits will be offered to all participating German institutions, replacing any current individual arrangements between Frontiers and those institutions which opt to join in this national initiative.
- Participating German institutions will benefit from Frontiers' institutional collaboration programme which provides dedicated workflows and support for university library staff, centralized invoicing via the central libraries or departments of those institutions and access to insights into open access uptake and expenditure via detailed data reports on articles published by their researchers.
- Researchers will continue to have permanent (open) reading access to the full contents of Frontiers' journals and access to Frontiers' Open Science tools, including collaborative peer-review, article and author impact metrics, and scholarly social sharing tools such as the Loop research network.

2. *Publication costs:*

- Researchers at participating German institutions will be able to publish in any of Frontiers' 79 journals, which cover more than 662 academic disciplines in open access with a simplified, streamlined invoicing and payment process (provided they are the corresponding author).
- The publication costs (Article Processing Charges, or APCs) of eligible articles of those researchers will be invoiced by Frontiers to the respective central libraries or departments of participating institutions and paid by them.
- A dedicated APC verification workflow will allow the central libraries or departments of participating institutions to verify and manage APCs.
- As this simplifies the publication process, a national discount of 10% on the APCs will apply for articles that will fall under the scope of the Agreement.
- Frontiers' APCs vary per journal category and article type. As journals develop, they may move into a different category, with different APCs, but Frontiers will not increase per-category fees during the term of the Agreement.
- The German Research Foundation (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft, or DFG) supports German universities by providing temporary funding for the publication costs in open access journals in order to enable them to reorganise their budgetary processes during the transition towards the open access publishing model. While some universities still depend on the DFG for funding, it does not always cover the full APC. Some of these universities are current members of Frontiers' institutional membership programme. For these current members to be able to participate in the Framework, and to ensure a smooth transition away from the current limitations of the DFG funding, Forschungszentrum Jülich and Frontiers have agreed to seek, during a national consultation round referred to below, a temporary and transitional solution to deal with this issue.

3. Forschungszentrum Jülich; coordinator of the pilot and participating institution

- Forschungszentrum Jülich, acting on behalf of the Helmholtz Centres, will co-lead the national consultation round (see next steps) with Frontiers and will act as an advocate with other German institutions.
- The Helmholtz Centres (as listed in Annex 1) aim to become participating institutions under the terms of the Framework, when finalized.
- The Helmholtz Centres will commit to fund the APCs (estimated to be a total of US\$ 2 Million at current volumes and growth rate) for their respective researchers over the next three years.
- A new payment mechanism will be tested under the pilot arrangement, Frontiers' *Advance Annual Payment* model, with the aim to make budgeting for librarians easier and thus to help reduce administration costs:
 - The Helmholtz Centres will pay to Frontiers a first-year *advance annual payment* of US\$ 500.000 at the start of the first year of the Agreement. This amount will be a pre-payment of APCs and will be credited against APCs of researchers from any of the participating Helmholtz Centres until that sum is exhausted. The APCs of articles published in that year after exhaustion of the advance payment will not be invoiced immediately but will be included in the calculation of the following year's advance payment.
 - The *advance annual payment* for the following year will take into account any credit remaining from the previous year's advance payment, or any APCs from the previous year arising after exhaustion of the previous year's advance payment. The three-year compound annual growth rate in articles from Helmholtz Centres published by Frontiers will also be factored in.
 - At the end of the duration of the Agreement, if the Helmholtz Centres are in credit with Frontiers, they may choose to use that credit for a new agreement, or to be reimbursed by Frontiers. If there is a net amount owing to Frontiers, the Helmholtz Centres will pay that amount.
 - Helmholtz Centres will not be liable for APCs of other German institutions and will not be entitled to any credits arising with those other institutions.
- Due to the above combination of factors (committing to centrally fund and pay all publication costs of all Helmholtz Centres for the coming 3 years, making annual advance payments and the national coordinating and advocacy role of Forschungszentrum Jülich), the Helmholtz Centres will retain the additional discount of 5% on APCs applicable to eligible articles under the current contract with Frontiers.
- Additionally, after successfully finalizing the Agreement which will put the Framework into place, Forschungszentrum Jülich and Frontiers will together explore potential future open access and funding models in Germany with relevant stakeholders, with a view to arriving

at a model which could replace the arrangements described here, with the aim of creating even more benefits to Germany's research community and which will further support the overall transition to Open Science.

4. *Frontiers' editorial policy:*

- Articles will be published under a Creative Commons open "Attribution" (CC-BY) license (currently version 4.0 and automatically updated as and when updated by the Creative Commons organization), allowing authors or their institutions the right to retain copyright.
- All articles submitted will remain subject to Frontiers' editorial processes, policies and conditions. The arrangements offered here have no effect on the peer-review, acceptance, rejection and retraction processes in place at Frontiers.

5. *Non-confidentiality*

- All arrangements Frontiers has with libraries or national consortia are publicly announced on Frontiers' institutional membership page: <http://home.frontiersin.org/about/institutional-membership>
- This Memorandum of Understanding can be made publicly available.
- Both Parties agree to make the final terms of the Agreement publicly available.

6. *Next steps*

- A national consultation round with the German universities, led by Forschungszentrum Jülich and Frontiers, will take place to receive feedback on the above proposal, to elaborate on any amendments needed in the light of that feedback and align on the processes, workflows and further details of the pilot and to agree on a communication and implementation plan.
- Finalization of the Agreement for the Pilot National Open Access Publishing Framework for Germany and signing that Agreement to implement the Framework, which the Parties aim to achieve during 2020.

II. **Legally binding provisions**

1. With the exception of the following provisions, no legal obligation for either of the Parties can be derived from this Memorandum of Understanding. In particular, there is no obligation to conclude the Agreement specified under I.
2. Either party shall bear its own internal and external costs incurred in connection with the negotiations and other relevant measures. Either party shall be entitled to terminate the negotiations at any time without giving reasons, provided that a declaration in writing to this effect is presented to the other party.

3. In case of failure to materialize the Pilot National Open Access Publishing Framework for Germany or to comply with the time schedules agreed upon, the Parties shall not bring forward any claim against one another, irrespective of the legal basis. This shall apply, in particular, to claims for damages or the reimbursement of costs due to failure to conclude the Agreement. The Parties, moreover, shall not be liable for information not being provided at all, or not in good time, or being provided in a faulty manner.
4. Any modifications and amendments to this Memorandum of Understanding are only effective if they are agreed in writing. This applies to an amendment of this clause too.
5. This Memorandum of Understanding shall enter into force on the date of signature by both Parties. It shall cease to be valid upon conclusion of all agreements required for the implementation of the project and in case the negotiations are terminated, at the latest, however, on 31.12.2021.
6. Should a provision of this Memorandum of Understanding be or become ineffective, this shall not affect the validity of the other provisions. The Parties undertake to replace such ineffective provision by an effective provision as close as possible to the regulation purpose of the ineffective provision.

This Memorandum of Understanding is governed by the laws of the Federal Republic of Germany
Signed on the date(s) set out below.

Jülich, 17 February 2020

Jülich, 17 February 2020

Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH

Karsten Beneke
Vice-Chairman of the Board of Directors

Dr. Bernhard Mittermaier
Head of the Central Library

Lausanne, 13 February 2020

Jülich, 17 February 2020

Frontiers Media SA

Kamila Markram
CEO

Frederick Fenter
Executive Editor

Ronald Buitenhuis
Head of Publishing Solutions

Annex 1: The Helmholtz Centres

- Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research (AWI)
- Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron DESY
- German Cancer Research Center (DKFZ)
- German Aerospace Center (DLR)
- German Center for Neurodegenerative Diseases (DZNE)
- Forschungszentrum Jülich
- GEOMAR Helmholtz Centre for Ocean Research Kiel
- GSI Helmholtz Centre for Heavy Ion Research
- Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin für Materialien und Energie (HZB)
- Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf (HZDR)
- Helmholtz Centre for Infection Research (HZI)
- Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research - UFZ
- Helmholtz-Zentrum Geesthacht Centre for Material and Coastal Research (HZG)
- Helmholtz Zentrum München – German Research Center for Environmental Health HMGU)
- Helmholtz Centre Potsdam – GFZ German Research Centre for Geosciences
- Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)
- Max Delbrück Center for Molecular Medicine in the Helmholtz Association (MDC)

Annex 2: Contact details

Forschungszentrum Jülich

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